

CONDITIONAL CONTROL FLOW STATEMENT: “EVEN IF”

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ABSTRACT

Programming languages are used to develop software programs via computer programming. In structured programming, codes are executed from top to down. Control flow statements are used to change the order of code execution of given program. With this paper new control flow statement is proposed to be adopted in the most common programming languages like C, Java, Lua. It is called as “even if” and can be used to evaluate given condition. If the given condition is false corresponding code block is executed. It aims to propose new functionality to the most common programming languages. It also provides a way to enhance readability of codes when it is used. Proposed statement can be used as an alternative to “if else” statement.

KEYWORDS

Control Flow Statement, Computer Programming, Programming Languages

1. INTRODUCTION

By this paper new programming control flow statement “even if” is proposed to provide functionality and enhance readability in the most common programming languages like C, Java, Lua, etc. Function of the control flow statements is to determine the order of code execution by decision-making. By using “even if” statement, if a given condition returns false then executes the related code block.

2. BACKGROUND

Computers are machines that perform arithmetic and/or logical operations. In order to operate computers require software programs. Programs are developed by using programming languages [1]. In structured programming, codes are run from top to down. Control flow statements are used to change the order of code execution. These statements are used to create dynamic programs [2].

Control flow statements can be categorised as conditional, loop and go to statements in structured programming. “if”, “if else”, “switch” and “ternary” are conditional statements. Based on the condition (true or false) particular code block is either executed or not. “if else”, “ternary” and “switch” statements can be used instead of one another. To create loops “for”, “while” and “do while” statements are used to repeat execution of particular code block. “break” and “continue” are statements used to go to different part of a given program [3].

By this study, new conditional control flow statement called as “even if” is proposed. It provides a new way to declare “if” statements. “even if” statement can be used in place of “if” statement like it is in “if else” and “switch” statements.

In the “if” statement particular code block is executed if condition is evaluated as true. By using “even if” corresponding code block is executed if condition is evaluated to be false.

3. “EVEN IF” STATEMENT

“even if” statement is proposed to be a conditional control flow statement. Usage of “even if” statement is similar to “if” statement. It evaluates the given condition like “if” and if condition is false then the corresponding codes in the block is executed. Condition is an expression that is evaluated to be true or false. Syntax of the proposed control flow statement is given subsequently.

```
even if (condition){  
    codes To Be Executed  
}
```

In a program which contain “even if” statement, if the condition is false then it executes the related code block. It can be read as “even if condition is false execute the corresponding code block”. Otherwise, the code block of “even if” is not executed and the remainder of the codes of the program is executed. In Figure 1 Flow Chart of “even if” statement is given.

Figure 1. Flow Chart of “even if”

4. IMPLEMENTATION

In this study implementation of “even if” is made by using C programming language. C is a procedural programming language. It is used for general purpose software development. C language offers structured programming features [4]. Subsequently one of possible implementation of “even if” in a C program is given.

“even if” statement can be implemented just by using simple text editor like notepad or by using Integrated Development Environment (IDE) like Eclipse, VS Code, etc. It is suggested to use an IDE while developing programs; since, it provides several advantages like code completion, error checking, etc. In order to create, build, compile and run projects IDEs make it easier to develop projects.

As an example, in the current study Eclipse IDE is used; since, Eclipse IDE is free, easy to use, cross-platform and open source software. Eclipse IDE can be downloaded from Eclipse

Foundation web site. While downloading “Eclipse IDE for C/C++ Developers” package must be selected. Afterwards, Eclipse IDE can be installed by executing downloaded file.

When Eclipse IDE is launched workspace selection is required for defining folder where projects and files is stored. Then new project is to be created while developing an application. In the Eclipse IDE under “file” sub-menu “new” must be selected to create a new “C/C++ Project”. While creating project “Classic C Project” is to be selected. After selection, project name must be defined and GCC tool chain must be selected. As an example project can be named as “EvenIfStatement”. Afterwards, created project is going to appear in the navigation pane which is on the left side of the IDE.

In the created project, two files are needed to be created by right clicking on the project name and selecting new file. Created files can be named as “evenIf.h” and “main.c”. Having created these files the following codes should be written in the corresponding files. Afterwards, project can be built and run by clicking on respective icons on the top bar of the IDE. The output of the program is “Prints if the condition in main.c is false”.

Code 1. “evenIf.h”

```
int evenIf (bool x){
    if (!x){
        printf("Prints if the condition in main.c is false");
    }
    else {
        // If condition in main.c is not false this code block is not
        executed
    }
    return 0;
}
```

Code 2. “main.c”

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdbool.h>
#include "evenIf.h"

int main(){
    bool condition=false;

    evenIf (condition);

    return 0;
}
```

The proposed statement is implemented as a function just to illustrate the idea. The implementation in the current study is just given as an example. In order to adopt better “even if” statement can be added to standard library in any computer programming language. Adopting the “even if” statement as a function or adding it to standard library can enhance reusability of any program.

5. DISCUSSION

Proposed conditional control flow statement can be used in programs to evaluate in the process of decision-making by checking if condition is true or false. If the condition is false then the corresponding code block is executed.

The same result with “even if” can be obtained by adopting “if else” statement as shown below in Code 3.

Code 3. main.c

```
#include<stdio.h>
#include<stdbool.h>

intmain(){
    boolcondition=false;

    if (condition){
        // Since condition is not true this code block is not executed
    }
    else {
        // Since the condition is false this code block is executed
        printf("Prints if the condition is false");
    }
    return0;
}
```

In Code 3 since the condition is false “else” code block is executed. Even though the output of the previous codes and Code 3 are the same, usage of the “even if” can enhance readability of any program. In addition to this use of “even if” statement can provide a new way of functionality.

The same result with previous codes can also be obtained by implementing the Code 4.

Code 4. main.c

```
#include<stdio.h>
#include<stdbool.h>

intmain(){
    boolcondition=false;

    if (!condition){
        // Since the !condition is true this code block is executed
        printf("Prints if the condition is true");
    }
    else {
        // Since the !condition is true this code block is not executed
    }
    return0;
}
```

Code 3 and Code 4 can also be implemented by using Eclipse IDE as explained in Code 1 and Code 2. First C/C++ Project must be created. In the project folder new file named “main.c” is to be created. Then the codes must be written or copied and pasted in the file created. Finally example projects can be compiled, built and run.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Proposed conditional control flow statement “even if” can be used to enhance functionality and reusability of programs. “even if” statement can be used in place of “if” statement. “even if” statement is simple and can be used to enhance readability of a given program. It can be adopted to provide a new way of functionality to implement conditional control flow statements. This statement can be adopted in the most common programming languages.

REFERENCES

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